

Silent Time A Form of Communication and Information Dissemination

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ABSTRACT

This expository paper focused on the relevance of silence as a form of communication frequently in use by religion worshipers, ordinary individuals, private organisation and public leaders. Silence in this regard refers to absence of any sound or noise. It examined silence on the basis of form, process, types, roles, power, as a dangerous tool in communication and application in different field of human endeavor. The author made some of the following contributions to knowledge among others: silence as an integral part of nonverbal communication; enables communicators to strategize information dissemination without distortion. And serves as a reference document for young researchers who would carry similar study on this topic. On this basis, the following recommendations were made among others: workshops cum seminars should be organized by communication experts to educate the public on the relevance of silence communication; individuals should learn to adapt silence communication instead of using offensive words that can generate crisis. the practitioners of silence communication should inject the use of body languages to enable them pass direct information to the target audience.

Keywords: *communication, form, information, silence, time*

Introduction

Silence is opposite of audible sound or absence of sound of very low intensity. By analogy, the word silence can be referred to any absence of communication or hearing, including in media other

than speech. Silence is also used in total communication in reference to non-verbal communication and spiritual connection. Silence indicates no sounds uttered by anybody in a room or area. For instance, the recent silence of president Buhari of Nigeria after the National Assembly Election was a source of worry to many Nigerians. According to Vanguard June 13, 2015 page 11, it disclosed that:

The controversy trailing the election of leaders of the 8th National Assembly may have been consequent upon the mistakes made by the National leadership of All Progressive Congress, APC. This sounds incredible. It was unexpected. Was it a coup, a broad day light robbery or just a fate? Why would the party suffer to wash its hands clean only to crack the palm kernel for its “enemy”. The APC returned from war called election. Yes, it recorded a landslide victory but later went to sleep. The worst was that the party thought that having produced the president, General MuhammaduBuhari who was successfully sworn-in on May 29, everything would be given for the asking of it.

Meanwhile, the paper declared that it was a lie. Before now, there were other hurdles to cross. By the Senate Presidency and the Speaker of the House of Representative. Those offices needed to be filled and it would naturally take the form of election, any kind of

election to fill them. The APC knew that. They also knew that they had the out-gone ruling party, the People's Democratic Party, PDP, their major opponent to contend with. But it is either they were completely oblivious of this fact or that they took things for granted. At a time in APC, both senator Bukola Saraki and Hon. Yakubu Dogara who are now Senate President and Speaker of the House of Representatives respectively were seen in most quarter of the party as enemies just because they were "stubborn", yes positively stubborn with their ambitions.

Infact, anyone who saw the national leader of the party, Asiwaju Bola Tinubu immediately words reached them that Saraki and Senator Ike Ekweremadu had been elected Senate President and Deputy Senate President would agree that the blood of an old man can be so hot when he is angry.

However, the alarming issue now is what the paper tagged "President Buhari's disturbing silence". Meanwhile, not a few party men and women were disturbed by the silence of President Muhammadu Buhari on the matter. Many had expected that he, being the leader of the party, could influence party's choice. Even before the election Buhari made it clear that he will not interfere in the National Assembly Election.

He kept his words. And this has elicited several subtle feelings in many people who are persuaded to think that a conspiracy of some sort may have occurred. But to be fair to Buhari, anyone who reason this way is yet to understand the president when he repeatedly said he had no candidate for the National Assembly top jobs and was not backing anyone. It will be recalled that president Buhari said that "he belongs to no one but everyone" during his presidential inaugural speech.

Meanwhile, silence in speech can be hesitation stutters, self-correction or deliberate showing of speech to clarify or aid processing of ideas. There are short and long silence. According to cultural norms, silence can be positive or negative. For instance, in Christian methods faith organization, silence reflection during sermons might be appreciated by the congregation, while in a southern Baptist church, silence might mean disagreement with what is being said, or perhaps disconnectedness from the congregated community. It is wise to note that silence

is also observed in music industry. When this occur, it shows time of contemplation to reflect on the piece. The audience feels the effects of the previous note and can reflect on that moment intentionally. Silence does not hinder musical excellence but can enhance the sound of instruments and vocals with the piece.

Silence is also observed in the legal profession. The right to silence is a legal protection enjoyed by people undergoing police interrogation or trail in a certain country. The law is either explicit or recognized in the legal system. While in the field of animals, silence showcases danger as pointed by Joseph Jordania (2009). Many social animals produce seemingly haphazard sounds which are known as contact calls. These are mixture of various sounds, accompanying the groups everyday business (for example, foraging, feeding), and they are used to maintain audio contact with the members of the group. Some social animal species communicate the signal of potential danger by stopping contact calls and freezing, without the use of alarm calls through silence. Charles Darwin (2004) also made a contribution on this in relation with wild horse and cattle. In another development, Nnoje Patience (2003) posits that "*communication is diverse as it involves signs and symbols*". Commenting on signum and index communication, she asserted that *the cry of a baby, may imply that the baby is in pain or that he is hungry but silence shows that he is in a good mood*. She added that there are other signs too that are used for communication by different associations or clubs such as *the Black Axe Club, Sea dogs, Kegites and Erudites*. These signs do not go beyond the members of the said association or clubs, as they are only people who understand and can communicate effectively with them. In like manner, some people use silence as a means of communication. For instance, if you talk to someone now and the person did not respond, it means rejection to your opinion or he did not agree to your speech. The recent silence of president Buhari of Nigeria after the National Assembly Election proved the relevance of silence as a means of communication.

It was disclosed on the 29th of June, 2017, by one of the State Governors in Nigeria that, the health situation of President Muhammadu Buhari has worsened, and that he has been on life support since June 6 at a West-End, London hospital. The cabal in the presidency would not allow him to resign to prevent the country from an avoidable crisis.

It was observed at a press conference in Ado Ekiti that, the president has spent 53 days in London to attend to his health challenges. Nigerians expressed regrets that no official information as to his whereabouts and his state of health made available since he left the country. The purported recorded audio message released by the presidency as the president's Ramadan message to Nigerians was only a damage control strategy aimed at further deceiving Nigerians (Fayose, 2017). He further states, *"the audio message does not represent the truth as our president does not only have voice impairment, he has been on life support since June 6, 2017 at a West-End London Hospital. The wife, Aisha, was not allowed to see her husband during her last visit to the United Kingdom – only three Nigerians who are of the presidents cabal are allowed access to Buhari"*. Fayose, challenged anyone with a contrary claim to produce the president to Nigerians within the next 48 hours. It is infact, that Nigeria drifting like the last days of the late President Umaru Musa Yar'Adua's government. He further remarked that he warned Nigerians against electing Buhari on the account of his age, health and mental capacity.

Furtherance to this, Fayose charged Nigerians to recall when the president's pictures were released to the press, claiming that president Buhari had an interview with Kemi Fadojutimi of 'All Eyes on Africa' TV shows in London on Monday, February 23, 2015 he proved to the whole world that the interview was conducted in suite 881 at Transcorps Hilton Hotel, Abuja.

Those who claim to love president Buhari had unwittingly advised him to hold on to power despite his inabilities to discharge the duties of a president. History recalls Buhari advised president Yar'Adua to resign his position and take care of his health. Yet, Buhari has refused to allow his deputy, Osinbajo to discharge the duties of an Acting president without hindrances.

History is saddled with political leaders who grab on to power at all costs. For instance, President Woodrow Wilson suffered a severe stroke while in office in early October, 1914, and remained incapacitated for seventeen months. Silently covering the development, it was inferred that, his wife forged his signatures on every important documents need to be signed.

In a related case, Franklin D. Roosevelt, was another classical case of sick American President, before the amendment of the American Constitution which

restricted the maximum terms of an American President to two terms, President Roosevelt set the record of winning the presidency for four terms. The peculiar thing about this president is that, he silently kept his vice-president, Harry Truman away from knowing any details concerning his health. He was suffering from polio and heart problems, but refused to brief his vice, Truman on the details of his meetings with Stalin and Winston Church Hill during the second world war, and with the connivance of the press, Franklin D. Roosevelt contested for the presidency for the fourth time in a wheel chair, having suffered partial paralysis from polio and won. He succumbed to a failing health in 1945.

Another interesting case was the case of John F. Kennedy. Very little was said by the press about John F. Kennedy's health problems with adrenal dysfunctions, rapidly disintegrating bones and Addison's disease during his campaigns. It was revealed that the president stayed on pain medications and amphetamines for the better part of his presidency. The press was able to shield these men in their political pranks from the public. These were possible because the American economy never nosedived in the course of their presidencies and also, the internet technology was not yet available to the public. But, in the current Nigerian context, it is a different situation. In Nigeria, the economy has nosedived, the high dollar rate is grinding the economy, a one-sided battle against corruption, the cabal is holding Nigeria hostage, the advent of the internet now empowers news to cross every space. Gone are the eras where the press and few political urchins can stifle information from the polity just to score a political goal. It is imperative that our leaders must tell us the truth at all times. The president should take the interest of Nigerians above his own so that the country can move forward. The fate of Nigerian and its people must not remain in the hands of the presidency cabal; our country must be set free.

Silence is also observed in the spiritual realm. *"Silence"* in spirituality is often a metaphor for inner stillness. A silent mind, freed from the onslaught of thoughts and thought patterns, is both a goal and important step in the spiritual development. Such *"inner silence"* is not about the absence of sound, instead, it is understood to bring one in contact with the divine nature. Many religious traditions imply the importance of being quiet and still in mind and spirit for transformative and integral spiritual experience to occur. In Christianity, there is a silence involving contemplative prayer and meditation. In Islam, there

are the wisdom writing of the Sufis who insist on importance of finding silence within. In Buddhism, the description of silence and allowing the mind to become silent are implied as a feature of spiritual enlightenment. In Hinduism, including the teaching of Advaita Vedanta and the many paths of Yoga, teachings insist on the importance of silence, Muana, for inner growth. In Eckankar the path of spiritual freedom, the spiritual exercises involve silent contemplation with attention on the point between the two eye brows with a view to make contact with the Holy Spirit which can be seen or heard in form of light and sound (Klemp, 2000; Klemp, 2016). This regular activity is known to have great ability to transform man from a pauper to a prince of God.

Suffice it to point that the human spirit longs for times of solitude and peace in this today's busy world. Individual can forget the pressure of competitive and the demands of family and friends and experience the healing power of tranquility. Transcendental meditation (TM) is recommended. *This means sitting calmly for about 20 minutes twice a day, eyes closed, the mind wondering where it will and silently repeating a mantra, a Sanskrit word that sounds like a nonsense syllable* (Oyebola, 2015).

Silence is an integral part of communication while communication on its own is gotten from a Latin word 'communicare' meaning "to share". It is the activity of conveying through a shared system of signs and semiotic rules. Communication in biology often occurs through visual, auditory or biochemical means. Human communication is unique for its extensive use of language. Silence is one of the branches of non-verbal communication which is studied in the field of biosemiotics. Nonverbal communication describes the process of conveying meaning in the form of non-word messages. Examples of nonverbal communication include hepatic communication, chronemic communication, gestures, body language, facial expression, eye contact, and how one dress.

Good silence communication is an essential tool in achieving productivity and maintaining strong relationship at all levels of human endeavour. The practitioners should ensure that they deliver a clear and interpretable message to the intended audience.

COMMUNICATION PROCESS

Nnoje, P.C. (2003) *described communication process as a connected set of human actions or operations that are performed intentionally in order to reach a*

particular result. Communication process is either a two way process or a continuous process. As a two way process, information goes from the transmitter to the receiver and vice versa. All the essential ingredients of communication are actively involved. The message to be sent has to be encoded by the sender who is known as the transmitter encoder. The encoder's function is to insert the message into a system of words, letters, signs, symbols, drawings, or numbers called code or language and dispatch to its destination receiver.

This message has to be sent through a passage or way called channel where the receiver receives and decodes. The receiver then becomes the receiver decoder. Message received has to be decoded by discovering all the meanings of what has been said or written in codes and interpreting them for proper understanding. After this exercise, the decoder sends a reply to the sender. This reply is called the feedback of the message received. The decoder now takes the place of the sender while the former sender becomes the receiver. This is why communication is described as a two way process. The exercise will continue if any of the receivers is not satisfied with the reply given. Thus, communication becomes a continuous process. It is pertinent to note that at any time one of them is sending a message, he becomes the encoder while the other person becomes the decoder until the exercise ends.

TYPES OF SILENCE

There are eight types of silence, namely:

1. **I do not agree. But I am afraid to tell you:** when there is an obvious power imbalance in conversation, there is a common meaning of silence. You are the boss and they may be afraid to push against your authority. So, even though they disagree they are staying quite.
2. **I have another idea. But doubt you will listen:** again, if you have authority and have presented your position with a lot of enthusiasm and zeal, the other person may hesitate to offer an alternative view as they think your mind is made up.
3. **I have no idea what you are talking about:** but do not want to offend you by asking question: even when you try to be clear you may be confusing. The other person may have heard the words you said but cannot figure out what you are trying to communicate. They don't want to say that you are making no sense. But, that's their experience.

4. **I am too upset to even talk:** I need some time to cool down and gather myself together. Something in what you said has pushed a hot button. The person is upset and rather than react, is choosing to contain their emotions. They are not saying anything but their body language is likely screaming – flushed face, clenched jaw, narrowing eyes.
5. **I have not really been listening.** And I am not really interested enough to ask you to go over it again. This is the opposite of four (4). You are off target. You haven't hit a hot button. You haven't even connected. They're not engaged.
6. **I am ready to pounce:** but don't want to be first to attack. This happens in meetings. The silence is a prelude to the attack, people are waiting for someone else to draw blood. Then, they'll eagerly jump into the fray and point to all the flaws in your position.
7. **I have unformed concern:** and cannot quite put it into words. Sometimes people have a hard time articulating what bothers them. They have got an uneasy feeling about what you are suggesting, but do not exactly know why.
8. **I am thinking:** What seems like silence to you is filled with thinking for me. People have their own thinking cum speaking rhythms. Some take more processing time before they are ready to speak.

ROLES OF SILENCE IN COMMUNICATION

It looks funny to say that the most important part of any conversation is silence. Silence serves many functions in conversation and how you manage it determines your level of sophistication in communication. Here are some roles to note about silence as a form of communication namely:

- (1) Silence creates listening space
- (2) Silence indicates empathy
- (3) Silence showcases emotional neglect
- (4) Silence shows understanding
- (5) Silence induces critical thinking
- (6) Allowing silence in conversation puts pressure on other person.
- (7) Silence indicates hostility or disagreement.
- (8) Silence shows profoundness, such as respect, aware or horror.
- (9) Silence paints a picture of contemplation.
- (10) Silence can be intentional rudeness.

SILENCE AS A SECRET TOOL OF COMMUNICATION

Communication is one of the basic needs of man just like food, cloth, shelter, water, air and medicare. It is a natural medium for understanding and reacting to our world. Learning, both informally and formally, is not possible without communication. Communication is the only vehicle through which we can process learning. The five senses of our body provide the communication channels through which minds perceive and acquire knowledge, skill and ability for our needs. In reality, though, silence can be a very effective communication tool. Communication however, simply means conveying a message, and sometimes silence can do that well than any words. You may have heard the statistics that 93 percent of communication is non-verbal. It comes from research by Dr. Alber Mehrabian (2009) that words convey only seven percent of our message, while the rest of communication occurs through our tone, volume and the like. So, if the majority of communication is nonverbal, doesn't it make sense that silence could be good communication considering its impact in human life? In relationship, communication often becomes a game of one-upmanship, rather than an exchange of ideas. The goal becomes to get the last word or have your ideas win out, instead of a sharing of ideas. When communication functions in this way in a relationship, division is fostered rather than unity. It's no wonder that "*communication problems*" is the top problem cited by partners coming to couples counseling.

Meanwhile, the followings are the three reasons why silence is used in communication:

1. **It enhances better communication:** many of us talk too much. All of us occasionally can be guilty of overtaking a subject to the extent that our message across in fewer words. Ironically, fewer words can result in a clearer and stronger message delivery.
2. **It gives opportunity to hear what's really being said:** keeping our tongue quiet frees us up to listen to our partners. When we are not running off at the mouth, we can focus on what other person is saying, plus pay attention to their nonverbal communication.
3. **It paves way to reach resolution faster:** the goal of communication should be to share information and reach a decision, not to win. Being silent at times not only reduces the noise but also speeds up resolution.

However, it is also important to note that silence can be misused too. Some people use it to express anger, others to hurt or punish their partner. It is commonly used in abusive relationship. Silence can be used for good as well as bad. So don't let any negative experiences with silence keep you from using one of the best forms of communication. It does take some courage to use silence as a communication tool. It is not always easy to do. Ironically, we can feel more comfortable and safer if we keep talking. It is risky to leave our words hanging without further explanation or defence. But there is power in that silence too.

Give silence a try. It can take some practice to learn how and when to use it correctly, so be patient and give yourself sometime to learn. But when you do learn how to use silence effectively, look out. Your communication will become much more powerful and result oriented. Note that not all silence is the same. This is because difference silence has different meaning. In order to get the conversation going again, you have to discern the subtext-the message and meaning hidden in the silence.

Silence as a Dangerous Tool in Communication

Communication theory typically has a lot to say about how we should transmit our message (carefully chosen, clear and concise language) and how we should receive messages (with appropriate eye contact, gentle acknowledgment and good attention to words and body language). However, silence as a tool within the communication exchange in both transmission and or receiving rarely rates much more than mere mentioning. And we often left with the impression that it is either an afterthought or an accidental occurrence. Perhaps, this lack of attention to silence is because most of us are at best ambivalent about its use when trying to communicate effectively and at worst more than little apprehensive about deploying it. In details, silence as a form of communication and how it is possible to use it both successfully and unsuccessfully. For instance, in kinesics which deals with ways in which facial expressions, the use of hands, arms, legs and posture affect communication. What posture do you maintain while talking to others? What type of gestures do you apply while talking to others? Remember that, these things reveal a lot about your attitudes and feelings to the other person. For example, in Chinelo, F.C. (2002):

a man was trying to correct his son for doing something wrong in the house. At a point, the son placed his hands, in Akimbo with a stern look on the face. The father quickly understands that his son does not have any respect for him. Without uttering any word, the man picked a cane and flogged his son in order to show that he cannot tolerate disrespect from his son.

The incident above illustrates an existence of a hypothetical situation where kinesics or body movement is used to communicate a lot about the young man involved in the silence communication situation. In the use of chronemics in silence communication, by chronemics, it means the use of time to communicate. A number of interpretation could be given to lateness to work. It could be that the person involved does not value his/her job. It could also be that the person is careless or lacks ambition to aspire to greater heights. The later arrival of highly placed officials reaffirms that they are superior to others. In Nigeria, people are often instructed to stand in the sun for hours, waiting for top government officials like Governors, Ministers, Senators, Presidents, among others who will come late to the function or visit. One needs to be careful in the use of time because, it communicates a lot about one's attitude in life.

It is very funny that dictionary defines silence generally as "*a lack of sound or noise*" and in the particular context of communication it means "*a period of time in which people do not talk*". Unfortunately, neither of these definitions are very helpful and they say nothing about when silence can or should be used, how and about what risk may exist in using it.

In two persons' conversation, we do expect silence to follow transmission of a short message, so as to let the receiver both understanding what has been said and then respond or to build the conversation further. But even this straight-forward use of silence can lead to several immediate problems such as:

- (1) The transmitter can talk for too long before allowing a silent "*gap*" to occur.
- (2) The transmitter may be unclear, meandering or complex in delivering the message.

- (3) The transmitter may convey disconnection between words and body language.
- (4) The transmitter may “*jump*” into the silence before the receiver has replied (or during the reply).
- (5) The receiver may not have been paying enough attention to the message.
- (6) The receiver may have become distracted or “*drifted off*” in part of the message.
- (7) The receiver may have been mentally rehearsing their reply to the transmitter.
- (8) Used as a device to signal resistance or non-participation by a receiver.
- (9) Extended for long period of time by the receiver (often conveyed as thinking/reflecting time).
- (10) Be left deliberately “*hanging*” by a transmitter to force a receiver to respond when the transmitter wants the input.

We can deduce that none of the above mentioned dangers is helpful to the cause of a truly successful two ways communication.

Meanwhile, the constructive use of silence in one on one communication is only possible when it is not used as a power play and without pre-set agenda from either party in exchange. In other words, silence is most likely to be seen as a positive tool when it is not used to exert any kind of negative influence on the other party or to be avoidant in any way. Silence is used in the conversation to build the relationship, allow quality time for either party who may need it. Naturally, this will depend on the type and style of conversation taking place, the topic of discussion and even the quality and depth of the relationship between the two parties conversing.

However, in general, positive silence is best deployed as follows:

1. When listening to the other party (listening face on, with good eye contact and no words or any distracting/contradictory body language).
2. Immediately after any relative short statement by either party, allowing enough genuine time for response before continuing.
3. Whenever an individual signals, it is necessary either by asking for time or more likely by appearing to need it through their body language.

In fact, most individual who are engaged professionally in communicating one on one, such as negotiations, dispute mediators/conflict resolution

experts, executive coaches, etc, in the business world go further in suggesting that communication quality typically increases significantly as an exchange is slowed down, listening is turned up and silence is much more of a natural feature of conversation on both sides before a reply occurs.

Towards A Theoretical Review

From Yochai Benkler’s perspective, networked public sphere is used to respond to the use of mass media as public sphere. He contends that the new information economy is the result of two significant changes. Changes in the processes of information networks from “*a hub-and-spoke architecture*” with multidirectional connection (Benkler, 2006, p.212). The second is the drastic reduction of communication cost as a barrier to communicate across borders.

The importance of this change is the increase in individuals’ capacity to silently act alone or with others; a change that potentially motivates individuals to play active role in the public sphere, rather than being passive listeners, readers and viewers of mass media information. The change is as much quantitative as it is qualitative. It is qualitative because an individual reorient himself in many ways: the inclination to get involved in discussion on matters of public concern, the potential to monitor societal and cultural activities and perform their duties beyond private sphere to that of the public (Benkler, 2010).

It is qualitative because information flows as it happens without the rigor of passing through an editorial desk. It is quantitative because everyone contributes to issues at the comfort of individual homes, offices, on a cruise as many times as it is noteworthy. Benklers, (2006) further points out that this change affects the relative power of the media. It affects the structure of intake of observations and views. It affects presentation of issues and observations for discourse. It affects the way issues are filtered, for whom and by whom. Also, it affects the ways in which positions are crystallized and synthesized.

The Power of Silence in Interpersonal Communication

Silence is the state of being silent, muteness. It is also a state of forgotten, oblivion. By interpersonal communication, it means a process of face to face interaction and exchange of message between (the source and receiver) two or more people usually

through their vocal sounds, sensory organs, facial expressions, and body movements and at times with a few mechanical devices such as the telephone, cellular phone, walkie-talkie or letter writing.

Meanwhile, silence as a means of communication equally triggers the power of pausing and its positive and negative values and culture. Silence as a means of miscommunication can also cause trouble, in the way the message may be misinterpreted or if enacted for a long period of time.

Silence and power of pausing is one of the important features of silence. Various pauses at times have the power to convey different meaning in different situations, falling into the idea of perception and valuation, pausing as a symbol of being in deep thought and pausing as a symbol of being assertive looking at the positive and negative value of silence.

- (1) **Linkage function:** silence may bond two or more people or it may separate them. Silence may heal or wound.
- (2) **Revelation function:** silence may make something known to a person (self-exploration) or it may hide information from others.
- (3) **Judgmental function:** silence may signal assent and favour or it may signal dissent and disfavor.
- (4) **Activating function:** silence may signal mental inactivity.

Having critically examined the positive and negative values of silence, let's focus on silence and culture. A look at this reveals that the value of silence in Japan derives from the conceptualization of the self as split into two parts. The INNER and OUTWARD. The INNER is associated with truthfulness and is located symbolically in the heart and belly. OUTWARD is associated with the face, mouth, and spoken words with deception, disguise and so on, whereas silence expresses inner truth.

As far as the inner truth is concerned, silence is the best way of expressing and maintaining it, while when the outward truth of the spoken word may be socially harmful and bring about criticism, hatred or humiliation. Silence remains the best means to concealing it. If you have nothing nice to say don't say anything at all because the power of speech can make or mar you.

Note that in relation, there are two dimensions in forms of silence which are complete opposite of each other.

- (1) By expressing their affection for each other through nonverbal means and in silence.
- (2) As an expression of social defence in disagreeing with someone, objecting to what has been said or done as a signal of anger and hatred.

Creating a sense of silence is indeed easy when one has mastered the rudiments and fundamentals of silence as a form of communication. Besides providing deep meaning through the mood of the actor, it also has a voluminous interpretation embedded in it.

Importance of Silence Communication

Silence communication is basically the keystone in nonverbal communication as it strengthens the bond and keeps the spark alive. However, the following are its importance:

- (1) Creates room for better understanding of issues and views.
- (2) Provides room for immediate correction of mistakes
- (3) Permits fast movement of information
- (4) Eliminates distortion of information
- (5) Provides room for the use of gestures and body movements.
- (6) Silence communication prevents the topic of discussion from being shared (i.e. encourages secret communication)
- (7) It paves way for peace and harmony in communication
- (8) It helps in cultivating the spirit of patience in our individual life.
- (9) Silence communication helps in building proper understanding between the parties concern.
- (10) It saves time and energy.

Factors that Hinders Effective Use of Silence in Communication

- (1) **Lack of focus:** you can't communicate effectively through silence when you are multitasking. If you are planning what you are going to talk next or think about something else, you cannot do well in silence communication.
- (2) **Inconsistent body language:** silence communication should reinforce the message you want to pass across, not contradict it. If you do one thing, but your body language conveys something else, your listener will likely feel you convey dishonestly.

- (3) **Negative body language:** if you disagree with or dislike what is being communicated, you may use negative body language to rebuff the other person's message, such as crossing your arms, avoiding eye contact, or tapping your feet. You don't have to agree, or even like what's being said, but to communicate with silence without making the other person defensive. It is important to avoid sending negative signals.
- (4) **Stress and out-of-control emotion:** when you are stressed or emotionally overwhelmed, you are likely to misinform people through silence communication.
- (5) **Cultural differences:** this is one of the major factors that hinder silence communication. This is because different cultural backgrounds attract different meaning to silence.

helps to create originality, uniqueness and direct information sharing. All elements of silence communication are interdependent and overlapping. None of them standing alone can make a good and complete communication. Okunna (1994) notes thus:

The connecting thread appears to be the idea that something is being transferred in the process of communication is referred to as the content or message, it is the constant principle of communication.

Meanwhile, the mood of the communicator in silence communication can make or mar the message. That is why it becomes pertinent to observe the rudiments outlined in this essay when embarking on silence communication.

CONCLUSION

As the quest to study silence as a form of communication and information sharing is activated in this essay. The focus on this essay provides a new point of orientation in using silence for effective communication and information dissemination. It showcases silence as an integral part of nonverbal communication that is capable of enhancing human relations. It is widely used in building relationships and also in different fields of human endeavour.

The reason for this is because communication is the only resources for functionality and proper coordination of every social, political and economic organization. Silence enhances mutual relationship and sustains development among individual. Creating silence for communication is about imagination. It is about creating the right atmosphere for the communicator to attract responses from the audience. In the view of Ike (1991) on story idea generation, *"he described fiction as ingenious attempt to use something imaginary to present a true and illuminating pictures of life, thereby enabling the reader to understand the realities of human experiences"*. It is a clear fact that, human beings because of one reason or the other usually have passion for or against something and silence communication also engenders the same degree of passion. The communicator's intention is projected through his mood. The mood is always the subject of attraction in silence communication. Another important element of silence communication is the inclusion of body language which helps in painting the vivid picture of the communicator's message. This

Contribution of Silence Communication to Knowledge

Today what one knows is shared with other people. Information is also knowledge when it provides people or machines with new facts about the real world. It is on this act that it becomes imperative for us to mention the contribution of this study to knowledge:

- (1) The study showcases silence as an integral part of nonverbal communication.
- (2) It enables communicators to strategize information dissemination without distortion.
- (3) It serves as a reference document for young researchers who would carry similar study on this topic.
- (4) The study enables communicator to strive and get themselves adapted with the dynamism of silence communication.
- (5) It enhances new innovation in accelerating nonverbal communication.
- (6) It also engenders secret information dissemination to the target individual.
- (7) Silence enables the practitioner to correct wrong impression or information.
- (8) It enables the communicator to emphasize on important point.
- (9) Silence communication affords one the opportunity to disseminate information to dispersed receivers.
- (10) Silence communication enhances relaying of complex information.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on this study and its significance contributions to communication industry, the following recommendations are proffered:

- (1) Workshops cum seminars should be organized by communication experts to educate the public on the relevance of silence communication.
- (2) Individual should learn to adapt silence communication instead of using offensive words that can generate crisis.
- (3) The practitioners of silence communication should inject the use of body languages to enable them pass direct information to the target audience.
- (4) Users of silence communication should vary their methods to avoid monotony or retard of interest from the targeted audience.
- (5) The practitioners should learn new silence ethics on a daily basis to speed their professionalism and open door for expertise.
- (6) They should make use of supporting materials such as hands on the jaw, crossing of leg, scratching of head and straight eyes contact.
- (7) The actor must make sure that he arrests the interests and attentions of the targeted persons.
- (8) Those that want to venture into silence communication should ensure constant practice to enable them improve on it.
- (9) Silence communication should be anchored on effective message delivery and on purposeful information.
- (10) The user should do it in the way it will facilitate quick understanding of the message.

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